

Objective

The objective of this project was to build two ArchiMate Architecture Descriptions (ADs), one for the eIDAS2 regulation and another for the NIS2 directive.

The goal was to create a structured conceptual model that clearly represents eIDAS2 and NIS2 requirements, facilitating their understanding and compliance. Ultimately, the final ADs enable the extraction of independent and documented views, featuring every relevant legislative concern, grouped by two **entities of interest**: eIDAS2 and NIS2.

Afterward, practical scenarios for hypothetical stakeholders, addressing potential real-world concerns related to both legislations, were implemented in viewpoints and views as extensions to the initial ADs, to demonstrate the applicability of the results.

Emphasis was placed on demonstrating the applicability of the project through these practical scenarios rather than conducting formal assessments. Since this is pioneering work, conventional validation techniques have yet to be defined. Validation through direct contact with stakeholders would require an entirely new investigation process. Despite this, efforts have been made to validate views using AI.

Contributions

To achieve the objective, a methodical approach was followed. Each legislation was systematically decomposed into identifiable legal clauses, organized through a traceability matrix, and translated into ArchiMate views. A dedicated numbering system that ensures traceability between the legal text and the architecture descriptions was therefore created. To maintain consistency and visual clarity, a color table was defined and applied across all views, while a set of explicit architecture principles guided modeling choices and ensured coherence throughout. The resulting ADs provide more than one hundred views and over a thousand uniquely identified elements, offering good coverage of both legislations.

Beyond representing the legislation, the ADs also include demonstration views. These take the form of practical scenarios, designed in accordance with ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 and associated to hypothetical stakeholders such as national authorities, agencies, and students. Each scenario was developed by first identifying the concerns of the stakeholders, grouping them into relevant viewpoints, and then modeling the legal environment through selected elements of the legislation AD. The views were built using a “high-level to detailed” approach, gradually refining the models to address specific compliance questions. In this way, the project not only clarifies and structures each legislation but also illustrates their relevance in real-world contexts, showing how stakeholders can extend them into their own “legal scenarios,” adapting the legislation to their business environment and representing it clearly in a view.

Finally, exploratory work was carried out on validation and documentation. While traditional validation with stakeholders was outside the scope, attempts were made to evaluate the views using existing resources and to experiment with AI-assisted techniques. Two complementary approaches were tested: a unit-based review with ChatGPT, which allowed small, traceable segments of the AD to be validated iteratively, and an AI-enhanced JArchi integration, which provided automated scripts for analysis, critique, and documentation within the Archi tool, using LLaMA and Gemini. Together, these approaches explored how AI could support validation and documentation of large-scale ADs, offering a potential pathway for future work in automated validation and enhanced refinement of complex legal models.